

Travel behaviour in contexts of security crisis. Explaining the daily use of car in non-central districts in Guadalajara Metropolitan Area, Mexico.

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Abstract.

Violence has worsened in Mexico in the last decade, and it currently pervades most of urban areas. More than 30% of Mexicans say that they have refrained from walking outside or taking a taxi. We tried to know how households that live inside this security crisis altered their quotidian travel behaviour. We thus analysed some official statistics, and carried out a survey in non-central parts of Guadalajara Metropolitan Area, where crime indicators were particularly dire. Logistic regressions were applied to know if households that perceived their neighbourhoods as insecure were induced differently in their travel behaviour than households in secure areas. Our research showed that socioeconomic factors were not so relevant in explaining travel behaviour in insecure areas than in secure areas. On the contrary, territorial factors became significant in such explanation in insecure areas. Most of the literature has related violence and travel behaviour by studying how the design of specific places as transport facilities or surrounding areas could induce fear of crime and hamper the use of public transport. Instead, our research suggested that violence extended in greater areas as blocks and neighbourhoods should be taken into account in countries afflicted by crises of violence. In such countries, public security measures appeared as an essential precondition to discussions on modal change or on sustainable public transport development.

Keywords.

Urban violence; public transportation; travel behaviour; car use; Mexico.

1. Introduction.

Almost 36,000 murders were committed in Mexico in 2018, according to the national bureau of statistics (INEGI, 2019). Estimations suggest that near 50% of those murders could be attributed to organised crime (Institute for Economics and Peace, 2018). Such levels of violence translate into a generalized perception of insecurity. More than 70% of Mexicans perceived streets as insecure in 2018, and 71% though the same of public transport (INEGI, 2018). The security crisis in Mexico is supposed to alter many behaviours, including travel behaviour. This paper tries to shed some light on how such violence modifies usual factors that other researchers have identified as modelling travel behaviour. Particularly, socioeconomic and territorial factors were examined in areas perceived as secure and insecure to predict the daily use of car.

Our research was based on a descriptive analysis of data from the national bureau of statistics. Such analysis was used to contextualise our case study. Besides, a survey was randomly applied in households at non-central parts of the Guadalajara Metropolitan Area (GMA) to generate the predictive models that accounted for modifications in travel behaviour. GMA is a conurbation that integrates 4.7 million people, and it is located at the western part of Mexico. It is a metropolis immersed in the same problem of violence as Mexico. GMA is home to the most dangerous drug cartel of the country: The Cartel Jalisco Nueva Generación. Guadalajara and Zapopan are the two municipalities that constitute the centre of the metropolis, from a territorial, historical and economic point of view. Taken together, they registered 32.7 homicides per 100,000 inhabitants in 2018. Tlaquepaque, Tonalá, Tlajomulco and El Salto integrate the rest of the conurbation, and together they registered a mean of 47.8 homicides per 100,000 inhabitants in the same year (INEGI, 2019). Since violence in urban Mexico shows a territorial dimension, the focus of our research concentrated in non-central and suburban parts of the city where insecurity is particularly dire. Such non-central parts of the metropolis comprehended a good scenario to analyse if perceived violence would modify the factors that explain travel behaviour.

The study of travel behaviour has drawn much attention since the last two decades. Two main routes have been used to explain why people select different means of transport. On the one hand, socioeconomic variables have been tested to account for travel behaviour. Income has been the most usual variable inside this trend. It has been used to predict the likelihood of using active means of transport (Guerra et al., 2018), and owning and using cars (Cameron et al., 2004). Income has also been used to measure the length (Suárez et al., 2016) and duration (Engelfriet and Koomen, 2018) of trips. Along with income, the level of education (Manoj and Verma, 2017), gender (Dissayanake and Morikawa, 2002), and composition of the household (Manoj and Verma, 2017) are variables that can be consistently found in the literature as socioeconomic factors that explain travel behaviour.

On the other hand, some research has shown how territorial factors influence modal choice (Khan et al., 2016; Cervero and Kockelman, 1997). Households in high density neighbourhoods (Hasanzadeh, 2019) tend to choose active modes of transport, as well as households located in areas with mixed uses (Lewis and Adhikari, 2017; Guerra, 2015) and a good design of streets (Peng et al., 2008; Cervero and Kockelman, 1997). The extension and the structure of the system of transport are also reported to condition modal choice, as more investment in massive transport (Guerra et al., 2018) and a good connection of transport stations with its surroundings promote the use of public transport. The relation between the place of residence and travel behaviour is of special interest for our research. Central locations afford more travel options (Susilo and Axhausen, 2014; Hasanzadeh, 2019) and facilitate the use of active modes of transport (Srinivasan and Rogers, 2005). On the contrary, households located at suburbs (Naess et al., 2018), and far from city centres (Guerra, 2014) are prone to use the car more intensely, mainly in areas where the continuity of urban fabric is broken (Khayesi et al., 2010).

Our case study is placed in non-central areas of a Latin American metropolis. Much research has concentrated on the peculiar urbanization of these contexts. Indeed, it has been said that urbanization in Latin American metropolises equals the extension of poverty at urban fringes (Kruijt and Koonings, 2009). The lack of public investment and support (Vázquez Castillo, 2004) is endemic in such contexts. The low quality of urban services motivates a situation of hardship and helplessness common for all the households (Sohn, 2011; Hiernaux and Lindón,

2004). As a result, urban segregation has become a leitmotif in scientific literature when analysing Latin American urban fringes (Montejano et al., 2019; Méndez-Lemus and Vieyra, 2013; Lindón Villoria, 1997).

Travel conditions in urban fringes of developing countries have been characterised by serious drawbacks. Longer travel times to get to significant locations is commonly mentioned in the literature (Lindón Villoria, 1997; Jacquin, 2012), as well as the lack of a convenient and dense web of public transport (Ye and Titheridge, 2019). Such difficulties result in people making fewer trips and remaining inside of their dilapidated suburban neighbourhoods (Behrens, 2005; Maricato, 2013).

Uncertainty and violence have to be considered when speaking of travel conditions at urban fringes in Latin American Metropolises. Globally speaking, it has been shown that the extension of neoliberalism has removed the securities previously underpinned by the Welfare States in the developed countries, and by the Import Substitution Industrialization in the Latin American context (Goldstein, 2010; Garland, 2001). Such changes at the global political economy have triggered that individuals face growing risks and uncertainty on a daily basis, and that the perception of insecurity has become an endemic problem since (Vanin, 2019; Dammert, 2012; Anderson, 2016). Counting on these changes, the fear of others, and the search for control are basic attitudes that lead individuals' behaviours in contemporary urban contexts (Dupuis and Thorns, 2008; Pow, 2013; Brunn, 2006; Caldeira, 2000).

At the local scale, the absence of institutional representatives (Zaluar, 2012; Schultze-Kraft et al., 2018; Chinchilla, 2018), and a deep mistrust on police forces that are seen as corrupt (Davis, 2013; Glebbeek and Koonings, 2016), are characteristics usually attributed to urban fringes. Criminal gangs have taken control of such spaces (Perlman, 2009; Desmond Arias and Davis Rodrigues, 2006) and turn urban fringes into disputed areas (Kruijt and Koonings, 2009). The institutional response often entails the militarization of such disputed areas, and institutional violence often criminalizes entire populations although they have not participated in illicit events (Campesi, 2010).

The territorial manifestation of urban violence in Latin American metropolises is especially relevant for the purpose of our study. The territorial basis of violence in Latin American urban spaces is so marked that there exists a concept to express areas appropriated by the different drug cartels: 'plaza' (Valenzuela Aguilera, 2013). Violence thus is the mean to control a 'plaza' both in a spatial and a social way (Glebbeek, and Koonings, 2016). In the fight against drug cartels, security forces transform such 'plazas' in *suspension spaces*, namely areas where an implicit state of siege entails that all rights have been suppressed (Campesi, 2010: 465). Low income populations trapped in such 'plazas' often lack social networks and resources to overcome the resulting victimization (Pare an Felson, 2014).

It is widely acknowledged that violence and fear of crime induce modifications in travel behaviour (Cárdia, 2002; Paydar et al., 2017; Figueroa-Martínez, 2019). Authoritative work by Jacobs (1961) and Appleyard and Lintell (1972) noted the important role that multifunctional and quiet streets played in preserving safe and vibrant cities for pedestrians. As streets and city centres deteriorated, more recent contributions have indicated that private vehicles have become the leading choice for individuals that want to travel safely in the city (Beecroft and Pangbourne, 2015; Loukaitou-Sideris, 2014).

The predominant explanation that relates violence and travel behaviour has focused on the particular design of urban spaces. Some characteristics of the environment thus induce fear of crime and deter the use of public transport. A dilapidated and disordered environment usually brings about the perception of insecurity and discourages the use of transport facilities (Atkins, 1990; Yavuz et al., 2007; Loukaitou-Sideris, 2012). In this regard, *hot spots of fear* should be detected (Masoumi and Fastenmeier, 2016: 113) and rehabilitated to recover public confidence and increment public transport ridership (Zegras et al., 2015).

In Mexico, Figueroa Martínez and Forray Claps (2015) have followed this explanation, and have demonstrated that neglected urban environments trigger fear of crime and hinder travel behaviour. Nevertheless, the particular conditions of violence in Mexico would require a complementary approach. The grim violence executed by drug cartels to control certain 'plazas' has extended a generalised state of fear and psychological hardship (Meschoulam, 2019; von Wissel, 2012/13). Thus, some studies have shown how a more general perception of insecurity severely restrains travel and the use of public space in Ecuador (Moser, 2009) and Mexico (Davis, 2007). In the Mexican context, the generalised fear induced by criminal cartels would exceed the fear that a particular design of urban environment can generate. Our study thus concentrated in the generalized perception of insecurity inscribed in blocks and neighbourhoods, instead of following the mainstream in the literature to consider environmental characteristics. In so doing, our research could contribute to the analysis of travel behaviour in cities troubled by security crisis.

2. Methodology.

The objectives of the paper were to characterise how travel behaviour took place in non-central parts of a developing metropolis like GMA, as well as knowing if living in an area perceived as insecure could modify such travel behaviour. A synthetic analysis of some databases from the National Bureau of Statistics was made to accomplish the first objective. Concretely, the paper shows descriptive statistics segmented for GMA taken from national surveys as National Survey on Households' Income and Expenditures, 2016, the National Inter-census Survey, 2015 and the National Survey on Victimization and Perception of Public Security, 2018. Such surveys allowed us to contextualise travel behaviour and the perception of insecurity in the municipalities that comprehend GMA.

Additionally, a survey was performed in March 2016 to test how the perception of insecurity modelled travel behaviour. Questionnaires were randomly applied in 800 households in non-central municipalities of GMA, namely Tlaquepaque, Tonalá, Tlajomulco and El Salto. A total of 100 routes were randomly distributed throughout the entire territory, and a mean of 8 questionnaires were applied in each route. Such sample size permitted us to make predictions with a margin of error of +/-3.46% at a confidence of 95%.

Individuals above the age of majority were asked a number of items relating travel behaviours, transport preferences and attitudes, socioeconomic characteristics, and perceptions of their neighbourhoods. Frequency of public transport use was assessed as a potential dependent variable, as well as frequency of car use and of active means of transport. Some statistical descriptions and some correlation tests were applied, and frequency of car use was identified as the most sensitive travel behaviour variable. The segmentation variables used to split the sample were the perception of secure/insecure blocks and neighbourhood. The following variables were used as potential independent variables to explain travel behaviour:

- Municipality of residence
- Continuity of urban fabric
- Distance to city centre
- Distance to municipality centre
- Household's income
- Education of the head of household
- Gender of the head of household
- Employment of the head of household
- Number of older adults in the household.
- Number of underage individuals in the household
- Number of disabled persons in the household

Logistic regressions were applied to calibrate the impact of some factors on the likelihood of individuals using daily a car. A total of four models were performed to account for blocks perceived as insecure, blocks perceived as secure, neighbourhoods perceived as insecure and neighbourhoods perceived as secure. The independent variables that resulted significant were the continuity of urban fabric, distance to city centre, income, education of the head of household, gender of the head of household, and number of older adults in the household. Statistics of model performance and statistics of model classification capability are shown in summary tables.

3. Results.

The GMA is a highly segregated metropolis. The situation is more evident at a neighbourhood level, although the contrast can be identified at a municipal scale too. The municipalities of Guadalajara and Zapopan got firstly integrated in the conurbation, and they obtained the best scores in many socioeconomic areas. Households in Guadalajara and Zapopan accumulated more income and could afford bigger expenditures than the rest of households (Table I). In contrast, municipalities that have recently been integrated in the conurbation as El Salto exhibited worse performance. Households in this municipality obtained one third of the income of households in Guadalajara and Zapopan, and spent one half of their expenditure.

Table I. Household wealthy indicators in the municipalities of GMA per month

Municipalities	Income	Expenditure	Transport expenditure	Public transport expenditure	Fuels expenditure
Guadalajara	19022.71	13634.80	2540.11	460.71	654.26
Zapopan	23065.30	16277.47	3193.96	716.29	943.75
Tlaquepaque	11907.76	7918.10	1657.15	773.37	498.76
Tonalá	13415.61	8753.09	1543.85	630.69	234.08
Tlajomulco	21100.70	9086.39	1720.95	357.13	369.30
El Salto	8667.89	6316.78	851.94	473.53	127.96

Source: Author's calculation based on the National Survey on Households' Income and Expenditures, 2016, INEGI.

Segregation existed considering transport measures too. Guadalajara and Zapopan occupied the central part of the metropolis. Households in these municipalities spent more money in transport than the rest of households located in non-central spaces of the metropolis. Furthermore, households in Guadalajara and Zapopan spent a greater proportion of transport expenditure in fuel for private cars, as they were the wealthiest households in the metropolis and had one or more cars. On the contrary, households in El Salto spent one third of the expenditure of households in Guadalajara and Zapopan on transport. As households in El Salto were poorer and could not afford to operate cars, they spent most of transport expenditure on public transport.

The use of the different means of transport, and the position of the municipalities in the metropolis conditioned how long households had to travel daily. The central and more affluent households in the metropolis took shorter commuting trips. As it can be derived from Table II, only 4.33% of individuals in Guadalajara that commuted by car, and only 16.67% that commuted by bus spent one or more hours to get to their jobs. Travel times to work were much higher in Tlajomulco, the other municipality with El Salto at the outskirts of the metropolis. Here 11.41% of individuals going by car, and 44.08% going by bus spent one hour or more to get to their jobs.

Table II. Workers that spent more than one hour in commuting to their jobs.

Municipalities	Automobile	Public Bus
Guadalajara	4.33%	16.67%
Zapopan	6.27%	19.92%
Tlaquepaque	5.15%	19.42%
Tonalá	7.50%	29.40%
Tlajomulco	11.41%	44.08%
El Salto	9.23%	29.19%

Source: Author's calculation based on the National Inter-Census Survey, 2015, INEGI.

Considering the results from our survey, travel conditions in non-central districts of GMA were detrimental. Public bus was the mean of transport that was used more intensely in a daily basis in the four municipalities where the survey was conducted (Table III). A 56.1% of the households used it every day. Our survey confirmed that non-central municipalities of GMA suffer segregation concerning car availability. While cars were used in a considerable extent (35.1% of households used it in a daily basis) they were out of reach for half of the surveyed households. Additionally, bicycles were used more intensely than mass transit, because coverage of BRT or light rail is sparse in suburban territories.

Table III: Use of different means of transport. Percentages.

Mean of transport	Daily	Weekly	Monthly	Never
Automobile	35.1%	13.9%	1.3%	49.8%
Public Bus	56.1%	28.0%	6.6%	9.3%
Mass Transit	10.6%	14.0%	5.1%	70.3%

Bicycle	20.1%	11.1%	1.8%	67.0%
Taxi	0.9%	9.1%	12.0%	78.0%

Source: Survey on transport conditions in non-central districts in Guadalajara Metropolitan Area.

This segregation has to be understood in the context of the crisis of urban violence that most Mexican cities suffer. The prevalence of objective crime in GMA is well extended (Table IV). At first glance, crimes against the persons were higher in non-central parts of GMA with the exception of rapes, that were more present in Zapopan and Guadalajara. On the contrary, crimes against property afflicted more the inner municipalities of GMA, as Guadalajara headed the rates of vehicle thefts and of house burglaries.

Table IV: Crime rates per 100000 inhabitants in 2019.

Municipalities	Vehicle thefts	House burglaries	Violent Injuries	Rapes	Murderers
Guadalajara	374,69	80,61	106,09	6,78	24,31
Zapopan	172,94	75,81	88,35	7,21	15,91
Tlaquepaque	191,81	65,19	107,50	4,07	42,91
Tonalá	243,98	78,90	113,04	2,98	29,28
Tlajomulco	164,35	76,81	131,04	5,82	42,04
El Salto	203,34	78,50	143,37	7,09	29,98

Source: Author's calculation based on the Executive Secretariat, National System of Public Security, 2020.

Such objective data did not proportionally influence security perception, as it is shown in Table V. Although there were a distinctive arrangement of crimes depending on the municipality, insecurity perception seemed to be evenly distributed. Perception of insecurity in the street, and in the public transport was high in all the municipalities, although Tonalá had worse outcomes. Nevertheless, such perception conditioned differently how individuals behaved if they lived in central or outer municipalities in the GMA (Table V). Respondents in Tonalá, Tlajomulco or El Salto consequently modified to a larger extent their behaviours due to insecurity perception than those respondents in Guadalajara or Zapopan. For example, 83.14% of individuals in Tonalá prohibited their underage children getting out alone –the double compared with Zapopan. Furthermore, 44.61% of individuals in Tonalá, and 41.90% in el Salto quitted walking outside

Table V. Perceptions and behaviours relating urban insecurity

Municipalities	Perceive insecure streets	Perceive insecure public transport	Prohibited minors from getting out alone	Quitted using public transport	Quitted getting out to walk
Guadalajara	79.64%	75.09%	61.58%	20.74%	32.14%
Zapopan	76.51%	79.70%	41.19%	13.48%	27.42%
Tlaquepaque	79.37%	73.30%	68.75%	12.20%	29.68%
Tonalá	82.27%	87.13%	83.14%	18.23%	44.61%

Tlajomulco	74.46%	83.20%	72.23%	11.52%	31.04%
El Salto	69.75%	75.18%	77.47%	7.47%	41.90%

Source: Author's calculation based on the National Survey on Victimization and Perception of Public Security. 2018, INEGI.

Segregation was a salient characteristic of GMA. It influenced travel conditions and travel behaviour in non-central parts of the metropolis. Households in such areas had meagre resources to travel and had to spend more time to get to significant places. Moreover, the security crisis that threatens many areas of Mexico modified travel conditions in GMA outskirts. National statistics showed that households in those areas modified to a higher degree their travel behaviour due to insecurity perception. The next step of the research thus consisted in understanding how living in insecure areas could modify travel behaviour as specified in driving daily a car.

We could not find a significant relation between perception of insecurity and the daily use of the car. From a territorial point of view, there was not a clear pattern to explain how the insecurity perception of the neighbourhood could influence the daily use of the car (Figure I). In northern Tlajomulco, a small fraction of richer households did not perceive their neighbourhood as insecure, and they used daily the car to a great extent. In eastern parts of Tlajomulco, and south-eastern Tonalá, the neighbourhoods were not perceived as insecure either, but the car was not used so intensively. Besides, in southern Tonalá there were many households that perceived their neighbourhoods as insecure, and could recourse to the car in a daily basis. However, in El Salto and in eastern Tlajomulco there were areas perceived as insecure, but households were not able to use daily the care there.

Figure I. Percentage of households per Postal Code that perceived their neighbourhood as insecure and used daily the car.

Source: Author's calculation based on the Survey on transport conditions in non-central districts in Guadalajara Metropolitan Area, and Google Satellite.

As there were no clear association between driving daily a car, and the perception of insecurity, it could be posited that such perception of insecurity could modify the factors to drive cars in a daily basis in non-central areas of the metropolis. Four logistic regression models were applied to find such differences in neighbourhoods and blocks of residence that were considered secure or insecure.

The first model integrated households that perceived that their block of residence was secure. As table VI shows, households headed by men were almost 7 times more likely to daily drive a car compared with households headed by women. Households with more than \$7000 per month and headed by individuals with post-compulsory education had more odds to drive daily a car too. Variables relating to the urban structure like continuity of urban fabric or distance to city centre had not a clear contribution on driving cars daily, and were not significant.

Table VI: Logistic Regression predicting likelihood of daily use of car for block of residence perceived as secure.

	B	S.E.	Wald	d.f.	p.	Odds Ratio	95% C.I. Lower	O. Ratio Upper
Continuity of urban fabric	0.413	0.255	2.620	1	0.106	1.511	0.917	2.491
Distance to centre in km.	-0.017	0.015	1.258	1	0.262	0.983	0.954	1.013
\$7000 and more per month	1.056	0.239	19.513	1	0.000	2.876	1.800	4.596

Post-compulsory education	1.121	0.251	19.974	1	0.000	3.068	1.877	5.017
Male head of household	1.917	0.415	21.347	1	0.000	6.797	3.015	15.325
Older adults in the household	-0.489	0.298	2.691	1	0.101	0.613	0.342	1.100
Constant	-2.935	0.545	29.058	1	0.000	0.053		

$\chi^2 (6, N= 444) = 107.055, p < 0.001$

Cox & Snell R square = 0.214

Nagelkerke R square = 0.295

Correctly Classified Cases: 73.6%

Hosmer and Lemeshow p.= 0.295.

When the block was perceived as insecure, gender of the head of household was not significant to explain driving daily a car (Table VII). In these blocks, there existed almost 400% more options to use daily the car when the head of household had post-compulsory education, and income was positively associated with the odds of using the car daily. Besides, when the block was considered as insecure, the distance to city centre turned significant in a negative way: adding one kilometre to city centre reduced 8% the odds to daily drive a car. Similarly, counting with an extra older adult meant that households had 56% less probabilities to drive daily a car.

Table VII: Logistic Regression predicting likelihood of daily use of car for block of residence perceived as insecure.

	B	S.E.	Wald	d.f.	p.	Odds Ratio	95% C.I. Lower	O. Ratio Upper
Continuity of urban fabric	-0.513	0.328	2.451	1	0.117	0.599	0.315	1.138
Distance to centre in km.	-0.082	0.027	8.971	1	0.003	0.921	0.873	0.972
\$7000 and more per month	0.814	0.300	7.385	1	0.007	2.257	1.255	4.060
Post-compulsory education	1.605	0.309	27.071	1	0.000	4.979	2.720	9.115
Male head of household	-0.014	0.328	0.002	1	0.965	0.986	0.518	1.875
Older adults in the household	-0.831	0.376	4.893	1	0.027	0.436	0.209	0.910
Constant	0.379	0.605	0.393	1	0.531	1.461		

$\chi^2 (6, N= 304) = 58.532, p < 0.001$

Cox & Snell R square = 0.175

Nagelkerke R square = 0.244

Correctly Classified Cases: 73.4%

Hosmer and Lemeshow p. = 0.542.

When the neighbourhood was perceived as secure, the masculine head of household was a stronger predictor of driving daily a car compared with blocks considered as secure. Table VIII points out that those households incremented three times the likelihood of using daily the car in secure neighbourhoods. Post-compulsory education of the head of household was the strongest predictor of car use in this areas, and households with higher income were also positively associated with daily use of car. In secure neighbourhoods, the relation between the number of older adults in the household and daily use of car was significant and negative. When the neighbourhood was considered secure, variables manifesting urban structure like continuity of urban fabric and distance to city centre were not significant in explaining the daily use of car, the same as when the block was perceived as secure.

Table VIII: Logistic Regression predicting likelihood of daily use of car for neighbourhood perceived as secure.

	B	S.E.	Wald	d.f.	p.	Odds Ratio	95% C.I. Lower	O. Ratio Upper
Continuity of urban fabric	0.079	0.317	0.063	1	0.802	1.083	0.582	2.016
Distance to centre in km.	-0.020	0.019	1.141	1	0.286	0.980	0.945	1.017
\$7000 and more per month	1.240	0.293	17.933	1	0.000	3.456	1.947	6.135
Post-compulsory education	1.439	0.327	19.365	1	0.000	4.215	2.221	7.999
Male head of household	1.099	0.454	5.874	1	0.015	3.002	1.234	7.302
Older adults in the household	-1.960	0.635	9.526	1	0.002	0.141	0.041	0.489
Constant	-1.957	0.594	10.849	1	0.001	0.141		

$\chi^2 (6, N= 307) = 84.494, p < 0.001$

Cox & Snell R square = 0.243

Nagelkerke R square = 0.336

Correctly Classified Cases: 74.6%

Hosmer and Lemeshow p. = 0.428.

When the neighbourhood was perceived as insecure, the strength of the relation between some socioeconomic characteristics of the households and the use of car in a daily basis decreased compared with secure neighbourhoods. In these areas (Table IX), households headed by individuals with post-compulsory education were the strongest predictor of daily use of car, but not so intensely as with secure neighbourhoods. Significant and positive relations were found between households headed by men and daily use of car, and between household income and this travel behaviour. When the neighbourhood was considered insecure, distance to city centre became significant in explaining daily use of car, the same as when the block received such consideration. In the case of insecure neighbourhoods, adding one kilometre to city centre reduced 5.6% the probabilities of daily use of car.

Table IX: Logistic Regression predicting likelihood of daily use of car for neighbourhood perceived as insecure.

	B	S.E.	Wald	d.f.	p.	Odds Ratio	95% C.I. Lower	O. Ratio Upper
Continuity of urban fabric	0.160	0.256	0.391	1	0.532	1.174	0.710	1.941
Distance to centre in km.	-0.058	0.020	8.736	1	0.003	0.944	0.908	0.981
\$7000 and more per month	0.791	0.242	10.680	1	0.001	2.206	1.373	3.546
Post-compulsory education	1.235	0.242	25.949	1	0.000	3.438	2.138	5.529
Male head of household	0.817	0.295	7.659	1	0.006	2.264	1.269	4.039
Older adults in the household	-0.324	0.261	1.538	1	0.215	0.723	0.434	1.207
Constant	-1.033	0.494	4.373	1	0.037	0.356		

χ^2 (6, N= 439) = 76.663, $p < 0.001$

Cox & Snell R square = 0.160

Nagelkerke R square = 0.222

Correctly Classified Cases: 71.8%

Hosmer and Lemeshow $p.$ = 0.751

4. Discussion

Our results pointed out that households outside central areas of the metropolis faced many hindrances to travel, and had to alter their travel behaviour when they were placed at insecure territories. In this context, perceived violence added a novel element in explaining car use. Zones perceived as insecure tended to reduce the weight that socioeconomic variables as income, education or head of household had in explaining the daily use of the car. On the contrary, territorial variables as distance from city centre became significant in such explanation.

Our findings suggested that households in suburban municipalities of GMA faced harsher travel conditions than households in the central municipalities. As expressed in fuel expenditure, poorer households in Tlaquepaque, Tonalá, Tlajomulco or El Salto used less the car, and depended more on public or active means of transport, something that is in accordance with findings by Guerra (2014) and Ye and Titheridge (2019). In non-central municipalities, this implied longer trip times. In Tlajomulco, there were the double of households that spent more than one hour to get to their jobs compared with households in Guadalajara or Zapopan. Prolonged trip times in suburban metropolis of the developing world have also been identified by authors as Jacquin (2012), García Peralta (2011) and Suarez et al. (2016).

Our research incorporated the security crisis that pervades much of the Mexican territory as an additional variable to explain travel behaviour. We could confirm that both, objective and

subjective indicators of insecurity were worrisome in the GMA. Nevertheless, both approaches on insecurity were not consistent, as objective measures varied greatly depending on the municipalities, and subjective indicators were more evenly distributed. Such inconsistency between objective and subjective data on insecurity has been widely documented. Collected evidence is not conclusive, as some research points out that objective incidence of crime influences public perceptions, while other research refuses such relation (Currie, Delbosc and Mahmoud, 2010; Abenoza et al., 2018; Litman, 2014). Nevertheless, it cannot be assumed that citizens' perceptions are misguided because they do not correspond to objective statistics, or that perceptions are not a reliable aspect to explain travel behaviour. On the contrary, some authors have suggested that it is often more useful to resort to such perceptions because they have a more straightforward relation with travel behaviour (De Meester, et al., 2013; Foster and Giles-Corti, 2008).

The perception of insecurity was well extended throughout all the GMA; no great differences among municipalities arose. However, preventive behaviours seemed to be more present in suburban municipalities. Thus, there were around 40% more individuals in El Salto or Tlajomulco that refrained from walking outside compared with individuals in Guadalajara or Zapopan. Some studies have demonstrated that violence in suburban metropolis in Latin America disrupts normal travel behaviour (Moser, 2009). Our research concentrated on these contexts of residence and shed some light on how the perception of insecurity altered typical travel behaviour.

The perception of insecurity reduced the influence that socioeconomic factors as scholarship, income or head of household had in explaining travel behaviour at a block and a neighbourhood level. Households with \$7000 or more per month were almost 3.5 times more likely to daily drive a car if the neighbourhood was perceived as secure. When the neighbourhood was perceived as insecure, such likelihood descended to 2.2 times. Moreover, households headed by a man had almost 7 times more options to daily drive a car in blocks perceived as secure. Insecure blocks made statistically insignificant that relation. Socioeconomic variables would not be so important to determine the use of the car as insecurity perception pervades all households, as it has been suggested by Yavuz and Welch (2010).

On the other hand, territorial factors gained weight in explaining travel behaviour when the block or neighbourhood were considered as insecure. Distance to city centre thus became significant in explaining the daily use of car in such insecure areas, although in a counterintuitive way. Studies have often shown that adding extra kilometres from city centre intensifies car dependency (Zegras, 2010; Guerra, 2015). In our study, one more kilometre from city centre implied 8% less odds of using daily a car in insecure areas.

In addition, insecure blocks changed the way how urban continuity influenced the daily use of car, although the relations were not significant. In secure blocks, the continuity of urban fabric augmented 51% the options to daily drive a car. In insecure blocks, the continuity of urban fabric decreased 40% those options. To summarize, insecure blocks and neighbourhoods increased the role of territorial factors in explaining travel behaviour, or altered the direction of such relation in a counterintuitive way. More research will be needed to clarify these phenomena.

Many studies have concentrated on analysing the relation between violence and travel behaviour (Masoumi and Fastenmeier, 2016; Delbosc and Currie, 2012). Some research

focuses on the design of urban spaces, and how some characteristics as lack of visibility or urban decay hinder the use of public transport (Soltani and Allan, 2006). There are studies that concentrate on the design of transport facilities to ascertain if it prevents the apparition of fear of crime and facilitates the use of public transport (Yavuz et al., 2008; Yavuz and Welch, 2010; Smith, 2008; Khan et al., 2016). Other studies reflect on ways to warrant security perception to enhance street walkability (Figueroa Martinez et al., 2019; Peng et al., 2008).

A slight variation of such explanation consists on linking the characteristics of the environment with poverty and income. It has therefore been suggested that low income households are located in dilapidated neighbourhoods, where physical signs of neglect could induce fear of crime and restrain all types of trips (Davis, 2013; Maricato, 2013). When such households are located in a suburban or outer district, urban space becomes a trap for poor individuals as they find many drawbacks in getting to better jobs or schools (Méndez-Lemus and Vieyra, 2013). In Mexico this formula has been applied too. It has been showed how run down urban environments trigger fear of crime, and inhibit quotidian trips (von Wissel, 2012; Figueroa Martínez and Forray Claps, 2015). Growing spaces at suburbs would concentrate such conditions that aggravate urban isolation (Arias and Rodrigues, 2006).

Our results incorporated the security crisis, and the perception of insecurity as a complementary explanation to the environmental design explanation. On the one hand, insecurity perception embedded in certain territories seemed to introduce a difference in the explanation of travel behaviour. Our findings showed that socioeconomic variables were less important in explaining the daily use of car in insecure areas. Besides, territorial variables as kilometres from city centre became significant in such areas. In insecure areas, continuity of urban fabric restrained the daily use of car, changing the relation encountered in secure areas. The perception of insecurity inscribed in some territories appeared to change the explanation of travel behaviour.

On the other hand, poverty was less important in accounting for travel behaviour in insecure areas as it was in secure areas. The literature usually associates poverty with derelict environments, and with fear of crime. On the contrary, our study suggested that the generalized crisis of violence lessened the weigh that income or level of education had in explicating the daily use of car. Perception of insecurity inscribed in certain territories should have to be taken into account to explain travel behaviour in countries afflicted by such security crisis.

At a global scale, it has been pointed out that the neoliberalism has entailed that collective ends and goals have been individualised. As Rose explains (2004), individuals have been made responsible for realising themselves, as growing daily activities now rely on the free mechanism of the markets. Thus, risks and uncertainties are extended conditions for individuals' behaviours in current urban contexts. Such uncertainties can also explain why insecurity perception is usually so remarkable in current societies. More research is needed to ascertain the specific processes that spur such insecurity perceptions, although existing work points to the role that mass media can play in underpin public fears (Lupton and Tulloch, 1999; Custers and Van den Bulck, 2011). However, our findings suggested that crises of violence and insecurity perception have intensified such uncertainties, and have to be added to explain travel behaviour in local areas.

In the security crisis that upsets Mexico, insecurity perception moulded much behaviour, including travel behaviour. Our study could serve as an antecedent for other researchers that consider travel behaviour in a country or a context with a pervasive violence that cannot be

attributed exclusively to urban design. Our study showed that such context lessened the weight that socioeconomic factors as income or level of education have in predicting travel behaviour. More research is needed to appreciate how a generalized perception of insecurity interferes with traditional models to explain travel behaviour.

The results from our study suggest that usual policy in transport planning and transport demand management should be reviewed in metropolis where the incidence of violence alters traditional models to explain travel behaviour. The stress on initiatives to promote a change in the modal share thus should count on a detailed study on how perception of insecurity influences travel behaviour. Many institutional efforts to encourage sustainable transport could get invalidated if poorer individuals at the city outskirts begin using cars in a daily basis, because of a very poor security perception in their districts. Either way, measures to safeguard public security should be a precondition for an effective transport policy in countries like Mexico. In a country with deep social disparities, such measures should not be based on police discipline only, but on redistribution policies that promote the capacities of the poor as well.

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